

The Prevalence and Pattern of Dental Caries in Pre-School Children

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Abstract:

This study was carried out to determine the prevalence and pattern of early childhood caries and its relevant factors in pre-school children of People's Public school of Bhopal. One hundred sixty two children aged between 3 to 5 years were selected randomly from the school. They were examined for dental caries on proximal & buccal surfaces of at least two maxillary incisors (WHO, 1987). A questionnaire was used for evaluation of related factors. It was found that 36.42% children were affected by ECC. Thus, substantial efforts by ways of both, early detection & treatment and effective preventive strategies are required to decrease the prevalence of ECC in pre-school children.

Key Words: Early childhood caries (ECC), caries in pre-school children.

Introduction:

Early childhood caries (ECC) is a devastating form of caries that may affect the primary dentition as soon as infant's teeth erupt (Huntington et al, 2002; Ramos-Gomes et al, 1999). Early childhood caries has been defined as the presence of any decayed, missing, filled teeth (dmft) in dentition of children under 6 years of age (Schroth et al, 2005; Drury et al, 1999) and severe early childhood caries (S-ECC) as any smooth surface caries in children under 3 years of age (Hardison et al, 2003; Douglass et al, 2001). The prevalence of caries in pre-school children seems to be on decline in most of the developed countries, but it is increasing in many developing countries (Holm, 1990). Therefore, this study was undertaken to know the prevalence & pattern of ECC in pre-school children of age 3-5 years in central India.

Materials and Methods:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was designed and carried out on 162 children of age 3-5 years, of which 101 were boys, and 61 were girls. The subjects were examined for dental caries. The WHO criteria was used for diagnosis of ECC. The mother of each child was also asked about type and duration of feeding, addition of sugar to milk feeds and

the age at which brushing was started. The data collected was analyzed statistically using Student's t-test.

Result:

Out of the 162 children (101 boys, 61 girls) examined, a total of 59 (36.42%) children were found to be affected by ECC. 34.42% (21/61) of girls and 37.62% (38/101) of boys were affected, but this difference was not found to be statistically significant. The mean of decayed, missing and filled tooth (dmft) score in boys and girls affected with ECC was 4.11 ± 0.53 and 3.10 ± 0.47 respectively, but the difference was statistically insignificant. It was observed that mean dmft score in affected children of age group 3 years, 4 years and 5 years was 4.43 ± 2.33 , 3.90 ± 0.53 and 3.50 ± 0.40 respectively, and the difference between age groups was statistically insignificant (Table I; Fig. I). The total dmft score of age group 3 years was 27 for boys and 04 for girls; dmft score in age group 4 years was 46 and 32 for boys & girls respectively; in 5 years it was 83 for boys & 29 for girls (Table I). The most commonly affected teeth were maxillary central incisor (Fig. II) and mandibular second molars (Fig. III). The least affected were lower anteriors. Most children had caries in both anterior and posterior teeth (Fig II & III). 45.76 % (27) of affected children had history of breast feeding and in 16.9% (10) bottle feeding was given. In 37.3% (22), both types of feedings were used. Most of children (89.2%) had the history of night feeding. In 54.24% of cases, sugar was added to the milk feeds. The mean period of beginning of brushing was 34.2 ± 2.3 months.

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Table I: Showing the distribution of dmft score among affected children according to age & sex.

Age Group	Male Children	Female Children	Affected Male Children	Affected Female Children	Total dmft score for Affected Male	Total dmft score for Affected Female
3 years	23	16	04	03	27	04
4 years	30	27	11	09	46	32
5 years	47	19	23	09	83	29

Table II: Showing tooth specific caries prevalence of affected children

TOOTH	MAXILARY		MANDIBULAR	
	Left %	Right %	Left %	Right%
Central Incisor	28.6	24.8	1.5	3.2
Lateral Incisor	20.6	15.1	2.5	4.2
Canine	6.0	4.2	4.0	2.5
Primary 1st Molar	18.1	19.5	35.4	35.9
Primary 2nd Molar	16.6	30.7	53.7	43.4

Fig. I: Showing the distribution of mean dmft scores among affected children by age and sex.

Discusson:

Different prevalence rates of early childhood caries have been reported from various parts of the world. These differences could be due to difference in favours such as sample population, age selection, type of sampling and criteria used for diagnosis of early childhood caries (Ismail & Sohn, 1999).

In the present study, 36.42% of children examined were affected with ECC (Table III).

Fig.II: Showing maxillary tooth specific caries prevalence of affected children.

Fig. III: Showing mandibular tooth specific caries prevalence of affected children

Askarizadeh & Siyonat (2004) have reported the incidence of ECC as 33% in similar age group in Tehran; our result corresponds fairly well with them. Febers et al (1997) have reported a low incidence (19%) of ECC in Texas. The prevalence of ECC in Kuwait, Holland, Tehran and Saudi Arabia was 19%, 9.3%, 21.1% and 27 % respectively (Al Dashti et al, 1995; Weerheijm & Uyttendaele-Speybrouck, 1998; Bargrizan et al, 1997; Wyne et al, 2001.) There was no significant difference between the incidence of ECC in boys and girls in the

present study. Wyne et al (1995) also reported the same. The pattern of involvement of teeth in our study was similar to that reported by Veerkamp & Weerheijm (1995). We observed that around half of the children affected were only breastfed and another half were bottle fed. Different theories have been reported regarding the etiology of ECC. Eronat & Eden (1992) & Hackett et al(1984) have suggested that breast feeding could be the cause for ECC. The present study showed that in 60% of affected children, sugar was added to their bottle feeds while Rodrigues & Sheiham (2000) have reported a close relationship between sugar consumption and presence of early childhood caries. It has been noted that in 90% of children night feeding was common. Wyne et al (1995) also reported that 3/4th of affected children were night feeders.

Table III: Showing variation in incidence of ECC in various studies.

Authors	Incidence of ECC
Askarizadeh & Siyonat (2004)	33%
Febers et al (1997)	19%
Al Dashti et al (1995)	19%
Weerheijm et al (1998)	9.3%
Bargrizan et al (1997)	21.1%
Wyne et al (2001)	27%
Present study	36.42%

Conclusion:

Thus, substantial efforts by ways of both, early detection & treatment and effective preventive strategies are required to decrease the prevalence of ECC in pre-school children. Educating parents and care givers, about ECC and its prevention methods will be a great step in effectively managing the problem of ECC.

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